

SKIN DISEASE MANAGEMENT IN AYURVEDA

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ABSTRACT

Skin diseases (Kustha roga) are one of the most challenging and chronic ailments described in Ayurveda. They not only affect the physical appearance of an individual but also have a strong psychosocial impact, leading to low self-esteem and stress. According to Ayurveda, skin diseases are generally classified under the term Kustha, which includes multiple conditions varying in severity, duration, and prognosis. The root cause is attributed to the imbalance of Tridosha (Vata, Pitta, Kapha) along with dushya involvement of Rasa, Rakta, Mamsa and Lasika dhatus. Acharyas like Charaka, Sushruta, and Vagbhata have elaborately explained their classification, etiology, and management. Management of skin diseases in Ayurveda is broadly categorized into Shodhana (purificatory therapies) and Shamana (palliative therapies). Shodhana includes Vamana (therapeutic emesis), Virechana (therapeutic purgation), Raktamokshana (bloodletting), Swedana (sudation), and Nasya (nasal therapy), which aim to eliminate accumulated doshas from the body.

Shamana therapy, on the other hand, involves the use of Kwathas (decoctions), Lehyas (herbal jams), Arishta-Asava (fermented preparations), Guggulu, Ghrita (medicated ghee), and Taila (herbal oils) to pacify aggravated doshas. This article explores the detailed management of skin diseases through Ayurveda, focusing on preventive measures, internal medicines, external applications, Rasayana therapy, and the role of lifestyle modifications in ensuring holistic skin health.

KEYWORDS: Ayurveda, Kustha Roga, Skin diseases, Shodhana Chikitsa, Shamana Chikitsa, Raktamokshana, Rasayana therapy.

INTRODUCTION

Skin is the largest organ of the human body and serves as a mirror of internal health. Any imbalance in doshas, dhatus, or mala is reflected on the skin in the form of various diseases such as eczema, psoriasis, vitiligo, acne, fungal infections, and dermatitis. Ayurveda emphasizes that skin diseases are not superficial disorders but originate from deeper pathological changes in Rakta dhatu (blood) and are often associated with chronicity.

In Ayurveda, all skin diseases are broadly categorized under Kustha Roga, further divided into Mahakustha (major types) and Kshudrakustha (minor types). The pathogenesis involves accumulation of doshas due to faulty dietary habits (e.g., excessive intake of milk with fish, curd at night, incompatible foods), lifestyle errors, and suppression of natural urges, leading to vitiation of Rakta dhatu.

The management protocol as described by Acharyas emphasizes Samshodhana (biopurification) followed by Shamana (palliative therapy). Along with medicinal therapy, diet and lifestyle modifications play a significant role in the prevention and recurrence of these diseases.

DISCUSSION

1. General Principles of Management

Skin disorders (Kustha) are managed with two primary approaches

1. Samshodhana Chikitsa – Elimination of aggravated doshas through purification therapies.
2. Samshamana Chikitsa – Palliative treatment through medicines and diet.

Both internal and external therapies are recommended to achieve long-term relief.

2. Shodhana (Purification Therapy)

- a. Snehapana (Oleation therapy) – Use of medicated ghee such as Mahatikta ghrita, Tiktaka ghrita, Panchatikta ghrita, Bhallataka ghrita. Purpose: loosens toxins and prepares body for purification.
- b. Swedana (Sudation therapy) – Done prior to Vamana or Virechana. Helps in liquefying doshas and opening blocked channels.
- c. Vamana (Therapeutic Emesis) – Indicated in Kapha-dominant skin diseases. Drugs: Kutaja, Madanaphala, Madhuka, Nimba, Patola.

d. Virechana (Therapeutic Purgation) – Best therapy for Pitta-dominant skin diseases. Drugs: Trivrit, Danti, Triphala, Avipattikara choorna, Manibhadra gudam.

e. Raktamokshana (Bloodletting) – Indicated in chronic Rakta dushti conditions like eczema, psoriasis. Methods: Siravyadha, Jalaukavacharana.

f. Virechanadhuma – Eliminative type of smoke therapy useful in vitiligo, fungal infections, and worm-related skin disorders.

3. Shamana (Palliative Therapy)

a. Kwatha (Decoctions) – Patolamooladi kwatha, Mahamanjistadi kwatha, Guluchyadi kwatha, Panchtikta kwatha, Nimbadi kwatha.

b. Arishta-Asava – Khadirarishta, Aragwadharishta, Saribadyasava, Chitrakasava.

c. Lehyas – Manibhadra gulam, Haridrakhandam, Amritabhallataka lehyam, Gandhaka rasayana.

d. Guggulu Preparations – Kaishora guggulu, Amritadi guggulu.

e. Ghritas – Tiktaka ghrita, Mahatikta ghrita, Panchatikta ghrita.

f. Tailas – Nimbataila, Karanja taila, Aragwadhataila, Mahatikta taila.

g. Rasayana Therapy – Bakuchi (*Psoralea corylifolia*) useful in vitiligo; Shilajatu, Bhallataka, Guduchi, Amalaki for immunity.

4. Diet and Lifestyle in Skin Disorders

- Avoid viruddha ahara (incompatible foods).

- Include bitter foods like neem, patola, bitter gourd.

- Maintain hygiene and avoid suppression of natural urges.

- Practice Yogasana and Pranayama.

CONCLUSION

Ayurveda offers a holistic and sustainable approach for the management of skin diseases. Unlike modern medicine, which focuses mainly on symptomatic relief, Ayurveda emphasizes nidana parivarjana (avoiding causative factors), purification therapies, long-term immunity building through Rasayana, and lifestyle correction. The combination of Shodhana and Shamana ensures not only temporary relief but also prevention of recurrence. By integrating classical formulations such as Khadirarishta, Tiktaka ghrita, Kaishora guggulu, and external therapies like medicated oils and leech application, Ayurveda proves to be a comprehensive system for skin health management.

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